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Brief Communication

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Community Participation Development Approach for Rural Development in Sociological Perspective

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Abstract

This paper is expected to understand the Community Participation Development approach and its application in society. Sociology is a practical subject and it always works and helps community development. Therefore, students, social workers, social activists and other people who are interested in this field should be aware of the community participation development approach. This paper makes a foundation for people who are interested in this sphere.

Keywords: *Community participation, Rural development, Sociology*

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Community Participation Development is an approach for rural development running with the help of people in society. Even though Most development projects are launched without taking support of the beneficiaries in society, the participation approach is not such a model and the beneficiaries have the opportunity to involve the project. This approach is totally different from other development approaches because this provides many benefits to the beneficiaries and also they work throughout the project and making decisions. Therefore, this approach is vitally important to rural development.

Community development is an essential and wide-ranging topic. It can be described as a continuous process in which members of the community come together to take collective action to create a solution to the common problems of community growth, ranging from small initiatives with a small group to large initiatives involving the wider community. There are many definitions regarding the community participation development, according to Hamilton (1992) defines community development as a planned and organized effort to assist an individual to acquire the attitudes, skills and concepts required for their democratic participation in the effective solution of a wide range of community improvement problems as possible in their order of priority determined by their increasing levels of competence.

Participation in community development refers to the complete participation and leadership of members of the community in the preparation, development implementation and evaluation of community actions or initiatives.

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Participation must not be tokenistic; members of the community must take part in a way that is relevant to them and to the project of community growth itself. It takes time for complete and meaningful participation to be established.

Community development is a holistic approach grounded in principles of empowerment, human rights, inclusion, social justice, self-determination and collective action (Kenny, 2007). Community development can be identified as people work together to solve their problems and fulfil meet the needs of the community. What are benefits of community participation development can be obtained by anyone who involving this approach? There can be seen many positive impacts on the individuals as well as society having community participation development approach. The following healthy results are generated through the community participation development approach.

Development of the infrastructure facilities of the rural areas

- Eradicate illiteracy
- Create job opportunities
- Providing sanitary facilities
- Demonstration of leadership skills
- Participatory involvement throughout the project
- Help people to self-awareness and self-development
- Eradicate poverty
- Collective consciousness

In the community participation development project, people gather to acquire their needs through collective consciousness therefore people learn many things from the collective works which really help people to bear leadership and sharpness their different skills. Involving the community participation development project people mainly earn dual credits, one is personality development and the other is an improvement of a current living condition which would be called the empowerment of the people. The organization of the following activities by the community group is called community development.

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- Identifying the resources belong to community and obtain optimum benefits by them.
- To accomplish the needs of people by utilizing the resources and planning to solve the problems.
- If it is necessary resources and technical support from the Government or Non-government agencies can be acquired (Athnayaka, 1997).

Accordingly, the community participation development approach is based on the needy community to acquire their requirements like water facilities, infrastructure etc. and the community also have more responsibilities and accountability towards the completion and its success. The speciality of this access is, needy people have to identify the problem and determine the best practical solutions for it. All the works are done with the help of a community group in addition to technical support would be made at outsourcing. In this approach, all the participants actively participate to make suitable decisions relevant to the project and decisions change intermittently where necessary moment.

Steps of the community participation development model:

1. Understanding of the community
2. Need assessment
3. Determine the objective and goal
4. Assessment of resources and weakness
5. Planning the project activities
6. Implementation of the project
7. Evaluation

The above steps are basically functioning under the community participation development approach. Therefore, social workers and other community supporters involved in the community development project should be aware of the above layers to support the people who follow the community participation approach.

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